

Silver Covalently Bound to Cyanographene Overcomes Bacterial Resistance to Silver Nanoparticles and Antibiotics

David Panáček, Lucie Hochvaldová, Aristides Bakandritsos, Tomáš Malina, Michal Langer, Jan Belza, Jana Martincová, Renata Večeřová, Petr Lazar, Kateřina Poláková, Jan Kolařík, Lucie Válková, Milan Kolář, Michal Otyepka, Aleš Panáček,* and Radek Zbořil**

D. Panáček, Dr. A. Bakandritsos, L. Hochvaldová, Dr. T. Malina, M. Langer, J. Belza, Dr. P. Lazar, J. Martincová, Dr. J. Kolařík, L. Válková, Prof. M. Otyepka, Dr. A. Panáček, Prof. R. Zbořil

Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Palacký University Olomouc, Šlechtitelů 27, 783 71 Olomouc, Czech Republic

E-mails: a.bakandritsos@upol.cz, ales.panacek@upol.cz, radek.zboril@upol.cz

Dr. K. Poláková,

Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute, Palacký University Olomouc, Křížkovského 511/8, 779 00 Olomouc, Czech Republic

D. Panáček, L. Hochvaldová, T. Malina, M. Langer, J. Belza, J. Martincová, Dr. A. Panáček
Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc, 17. listopadu 1192/12, 771 46 Olomouc, Czech Republic

Dr. R. Večeřová, Prof. M. Kolář

Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry, Palacký University Olomouc, Hněvotínská 3, 775 15 Olomouc, Czech Republic

Prof. R. Zbořil, Dr. A. Bakandritsos

Nanotechnology Centre, Centre of Energy and Environmental Technologies, VŠB–Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

Abstract

The ability of bacteria to develop resistance to antibiotics is threatening one of the pillars of modern medicine. It was recently understood that bacteria can develop resistance even to silver nanoparticles by producing flagellin, a protein that induces their aggregation and deactivation. This study shows that silver covalently bound to cyanographene sheets (GCN/Ag) kills silver-nanoparticle-resistant bacteria at concentrations thirty times lower than silver nanoparticles, a challenge that has been so far unmet. Tested also against multi-drug resistant strains, the antibacterial activity of GCN/Ag is systematically found as potent as that

of free ionic silver, 10 nm colloidal silver nanoparticles, and other top-performing silver-based hybrids. Due to the strong and multiple dative bonds between the nitrile groups of GCN and silver, as theory and experiments confirm, there is marginal silver ion leaching, even after six months of storage, and thus very high cytocompatibility to human cells. Molecular dynamics simulations suggest a strong interaction of GCN/Ag with the bacterial membrane, and as corroborated by experiments, the antibacterial activity does not rely on the release of silver nanoparticles or ions. Endowed with these properties, GCN/Ag shows that rigid supports selectively and densely functionalized with potent silver-binding ligands, such as cyanographene, may open new avenues against microbial resistance.